

QUIZ**LAST NAME: TEMBO****FIRST NAME: DUMIZULU****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. LAURENT CLEENEWERCK****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord2007 (e.g., MSWord 2010 on Windows 7)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Why are citations important in research and academic writing?

- To give credit where it is due and avoid plagiarism¹**
- So that the document looks neat and presentable
- To establish the credibility of your own work
- None of the above

2. In academic and research writing citations are used when

- Quoting, summarizing or paraphrasing other people's work²**
- Only when long quoting other peoples' material

¹ ACA-01 Coursepack Period 1 (EUCLID University, 2015), 11–14, accessed April 29, 2019, https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf_.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, Chicago 60637, 2013), 51–52.

- Only when you copy word for word from a source
 - When you only want to back up your own ideas
3. **The Turabian author-date style of in-text citation follows which order of the elements?**
- Author-date and page number³**
 - Author and date only
 - Elements can be ordered anyhow
 - Source title and date
4. **The Write Source 2000 is a guide to writing, thinking and learning that was designed to**
- Serve as a personal writing and learning guide⁴**
 - Help students cut and paste other people's ideas
 - Tell students how to write their papers
 - None of the above
5. **Which of the following is not a general rule of the University of Oxford style guide**
- Use capital letters to emphasize a point⁵**

³ Ibid., 87.

⁴ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999), 3.

⁵ ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 4, Egnyte, 99, last modified 2015, accessed June 19, 2019, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/YlJXVLgPv0/>.

- Use lower case wherever possible
 - Close up spaces and don't use full stops in abbreviations (e.g., 6pm)
 - Only write out numbers up to ten and use figures for 11 onwards
6. **The University of Oxford style guide was written to provide the staff with a standard form for communicating across the university's written communication. It does not recommend**
- Public use nor competition with other professional writing guides and dictionaries⁶**
 - Using the least amount of space and ink
 - Using lower case letters whenever possible
 - Using punctuations only when necessary that it does not change the meaning of the sentence
7. **The Harvard rule of style is similar to the Turabian style in such a way that**
- It is Author-date style of referencing⁷**
 - It is a numeric system which uses numbers for in-text citations
 - It contains information about the primary source
 - A reference list does not appear at the end of the document
8. **Which of the following is not an example of irrelevant information presented in research writing?**
- Material appropriate and relevant for the readership⁸**

⁶ Ibid., 99.

⁷ Ibid., 74.

- Unnecessary background
 - Anecdotal information
 - Subjectivity and use of superlatives
9. **The Bluebook style guide is mostly used by law students, lawyers, judges and other legal professionals. The principle elements of a citation are composed of**
- A signal demonstrating the relationship between the proposition and the source, the source or authority, and parenthetical information which explains the relevance of the cited authority⁹**
 - A signal demonstrating the relationship between the proposition and the source, parenthetical information which explains the relevance of the cited authority
 - A signal demonstrating the relationship between the proposition and the source, the source or authority and date information was accessed.
 - All of the above
10. **Being an international organisation, WHO is mindful of its language and aims to address all people equally and fairly by**
- Using language that is not discriminatory against, stereotype or demeans people on the basis of their sex, ethnicity, physical or intellectual impairments, or age¹⁰**
 - Politely referring to people by their first names

⁸ Ibid., 8–9.

⁹ The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citations, 2010, 5, accessed June 26, 2019, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/IWqN4UDvYk/>.

¹⁰ WHO Style Guide, Egnyte, 55–58, last modified 2004, accessed June 27, 2019, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/wX6ShMd3OF/>.

- Using language that is discriminatory against, stereotype or demeans people on the basis of their sex, ethnicity, physical or intellectual impairments, or age
- By grouping people based on their racial or cultural background

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ACA-01 Coursepack. EUCLID University, 2019. Accessed April 29, 2019. https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf_.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.